

FEASIBILITY STUDY OF A 3D-PRINTED HONEYCOMB CORE STRUCTURE AS THERMAL VACUUM INSULATION FOR LIQUID HYDROGEN COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSELS

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ABSTRACT

Due to its approximately three times higher energy density by mass compared to conventional kerosene, hydrogen is one of the most promising technologies for reducing CO₂ emissions in aviation. However, the energy density by volume is significantly lower than that of kerosene. For example, three thousand liters of gaseous hydrogen correspond only to the energy content of one liter of kerosene at ambient conditions (pressure, temperature). In the automotive sector, this problem is often solved by storing the gaseous hydrogen at a high pressure of 700 bar. Although this approach has already led to a significant improvement, it is still not sufficient for aircrafts, as weight and volume are particularly critical factors here. A further increase in energy density can only be achieved by cooling the hydrogen to 20 K (-253°C), where gaseous hydrogen turns into liquid hydrogen. At 20 K, four liters of liquid hydrogen correspond approximately to the energy density of one liter of kerosene. In order to maintain these cryogenic temperatures and minimize evaporation losses (boil-off), special requirements are placed on the cryogenic storage tanks and in particular on their insulation. Some of these cryogenic storage tanks consist of load-bearing double-wall concepts in which a vacuum ensures thermal insulation, which served as baseline for this study. The authors examined CFRP sandwich structures with 3D-printed honeycomb cores in terms of their manufacturability and their thermal insulation properties at cryogenic temperatures. 3D printing of the cores was chosen due to its advantages with respect to design freedom especially for curved structures such as tank domes but also due to its possibility of local reinforcement in areas of load introduction by means of adjustable cell density and cell wall thicknesses, anti-telegraphing design elements etc. [1]. A further advantage is the possibility to use materials with low outgassing behavior e.g. PEEK [2].

1 INTRODUCTION

The shift toward zero-emission aviation demanded innovative solutions for onboard energy storage and structural integration. Liquid hydrogen (LH₂) offered high energy density but required cryogenic

containment, which posed significant challenges for lightweight aircraft structures. This study was conducted within the framework of the CryoFuselage project, which focused on the development of insulated LH₂ tanks made from CFRP. A key objective was the integration of such tanks into load-bearing fuselage structures to enable multifunctionality and weight savings.

As a representative application case, a regional turboprop aircraft was used as an example in which a cylindrical LH₂ tank was integrated into the aft fuselage (see **Fig. 1**). Therefore, a load-bearing evacuated core concept with 3D-printed cores was chosen for the thermal insulation layer.

Figure 1: Schematic view of LH₂ tank in fuselage aft section

2 STATE OF THE ART: THERMAL INSULATION FOR CRYOGENIC HYDROGEN TANKS

2.1 Foam Insulation

Closed-cell foams (e.g., PU, PIR) are widely used due to ease of application and low cost. However, performance deteriorates under cryogenic conditions, and long-term dimensional stability is limited. Polyurethane (PU), polyisocyanurate (PIR), or PMI foams (e.g., ROHACELL) are established as closed-cell insulators. Their typical thermal conductivity is between 20–100 K [3-5]. They have been used, for example, in the Lockheed CL-400 [3] and in Space Shuttle tanks as spray-on foam insulation [4-5]. Oehlke [6] validates them for smaller aircraft tanks for an ATR 72, while Swanger and Fesmire [10] document mechanical and thermal aging under cryogenic cycling.

- Advantages: inexpensive, low density, simple application, load-bearing for small tank [6]
- Disadvantages: shrinkage, cracking, delamination under cycling [5-7]

2.2 Multilayer Insulation (MLI)

MLI uses alternating reflective and spacer layers and performs best under vacuum. It is highly effective against radiative heat transfer but fragile. MLI performance relies on maintaining a high vacuum and preserving separation between its reflective layers. Compression, crimping, or misalignment can collapse the insulating gaps, drastically increasing thermal conductivity. MLI cannot carry mechanical loads and must be decoupled from structural stress paths. This limits its integration in tank systems exposed to fuselage loads or direct mounting via Y-joints. Handling damage, installation variability, and lack of load-sharing capacity are key constraints. MLI systems consisting of reflective films and spacers can achieve $<1 \text{ mW/m}\cdot\text{K}$ under high vacuum ($<10^{-3} \text{ Pa}$) [4], [6], [8]. Widely used in space applications [3], [8], they are not structurally load-bearing. Johnson [8] describes performance variability depending on the number of layers, compression, and penetrations. Swanger [4] points out outgassing and compression issues. Oehlke [6] documents a drastic increase in thermal conductivity in case of vacuum loss ($\times 100\text{--}2000$).

- Advantages: lowest thermal conductivity, very lightweight
- Disadvantages: sensitive to compression/folding, not load-bearing, high vacuum requirement [4], [6], [8]

Extensions: VDMLI and VCS

To address the limitations of classical MLI, advancements such as Variable Density MLI (VDMLI) and Vapor Cooled Shields (VCS) have been developed. Zheng et al. compare four insulation systems (MLI, MLI+VCS, VDMLI, VDMLI+VCS) and show that the combination VDMLI+VCS is thermally the most effective [9]. Wang et al. model hybrid concepts with HGM and MLI [10].

- Advantages: reduced thermal conductivity, targeted thermal optimization
- Disadvantages: not load-bearing, complex integration, vacuum still required [9], [10]

2.3 Perlite, Aerogels, HGM, Fiber-Based Insulators

Powder, granular, and fiber-based fillers (perlite, aerogel, hollow glass microspheres, glass wool) combine moderate insulation performance (10–50 mW/m·K) with more robust structure [4-5], [10-11]. Swanger [4] and Wilken [11] demonstrate stability under vacuum loss, though with higher weight. Modeling studies by Wang et al. [10] show advantages through variable density combinations.

- Advantages: robust, moderate performance, partially reusable
- Disadvantages: heavier than MLI, less geometric flexibility [4], [10-11]

2.4 Double-Wall Vacuum Insulation

Vacuum insulation uses a sealed, evacuated gap between tank walls to minimize convective and conductive heat transfer. It offers high insulation performance and can be combined with reflective coatings. A proven space architecture with an evacuated interspace. Applications include Space Shuttle ET, Delta IV, and X-33 [3], [7], [12]. Thermally efficient (<1 mW/m·K) but heavy and complex to assemble. Brewer [3] and Adler [7] describe the advantages; Johnson [12] emphasizes integration complexity.

- Advantages: high efficiency, optionally combinable with MLI [3], [7], [12]
- Disadvantages: double-wall structure, weight, complex around dome geometries [7], [12]

2.5 Evacuated Structural Sandwich Core

Sandwich structures with an evacuable cell core (e.g., perforated honeycomb) combine structural and insulation functions. The concept was introduced by Northrop Grumman in the NASA CCTD [12]; further developments in European studies (PHOEBUS, ICARUS) [13], Brewer [3] mentions early structural honeycomb approaches.

- Advantages: insulation & structure, low thermal conductivity, integrative
- Disadvantages: vacuum tightness, manufacturing complexity [3], [12-13]

3 DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING

3.1 Concept Rationale

As a thermal insulation solution, this work adopts the concept of vacuum insulation based on the Evacuated Core principle [12-13]. This approach is characterized by good thermal performance at cryogenic temperatures and the ability to structurally integrate the insulation into load-bearing components. As described in Section 2.5, this involves e.g. embedding perforated honeycomb cores into a sandwich structure and subsequently evacuating the internal cavity. Standard methods use pointwise needle-perforated or slotted Nomex honeycomb cores to ensure uniform pressure distribution and enable

outgassing. However, conventional approaches are associated with several drawbacks:

- Perforation displaces cell wall material locally, which can lead to unstable membrane regions during evacuation. These areas may deform under vacuum, a phenomenon which can be described informally as “flap effect.”
- Slotted cores exhibit reduced mechanical integrity, particularly at the interface with the face sheets, as both the continuous bonding surface and the cellular structure are interrupted.
- Traditional honeycomb structures are optimized for planar or single curved surfaces. When applied to double curved geometries (e.g., spherical domes), they suffer from the so-called saddle effect: the hexagonal cells twist or collapse due to forced adaptation, leading to geometric distortion and a significant reduction in mechanical properties [1]

3.2 Core Design

As part of the concept validation for a vacuum-insulated sandwich insulation system, an innovative approach using a 3D-printed, perforated honeycomb core was selected. This core architecture combines load-bearing capacity and thermal insulation within a single functional element. The required venting perforations are directly integrated during the additive manufacturing process, as illustrated in **Fig.2**.

Figure 2: Perforated honeycomb

Key advantages of the 3D-printed design include design flexibility, the use of materials with low thermal conductivity and minimal outgassing (e.g., PEEK/GF), and the potential for functional integration, such as localized reinforcements or anti-telegraphing and snap-in coupling features, as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: (a) anti-telegraphing solution; (b) honeycomb with snap-in connections [1]

However, challenges remain regarding the limited industrial maturity of the materials and processes involved, as well as the process-dependent variability in mechanical properties. One key challenge is to ensure that the materials withstand the temperature and pressure conditions of the autoclave process. The HT-PLA used in initial trials, with a heat deflection temperature (HDT) of 180 °C, proved unsuitable for autoclave curing at 130°C and an autoclave pressure of 2 bar. In contrast, the fabrication of a small sandwich panel using a 3D-printed PEEK/GF honeycomb with anti-telegraphing solution (spider-web) structure was successful. The printing was carried out on a high-performance polymer printer (INTAMSYS 410 Pro) acquired in 2024. **Fig. 4** shows both small sandwich panels, the collapsed HT-

PLA and the PEEK/GF.

Figure 4: Autoclave process 130°C/2 bar: (a) collapsed honeycomb core with HT-PLA (HDT = 180 °C) - 2022; (b) intact honeycomb core with PEEK/GF (HDT = 300 °C) - 2024

3.3 Vacuum Panel Manufacturing

Due to printer limitations with respect to material and building space, four honeycomb core segments (each 187.6 mm × 144.3 mm × 20 mm) were printed and subsequently bonded together with a paste adhesive to form the full-size core tested in the vacuum insulation test. Future designs will consider the use of snap-in connectors, as illustrated in Fig. 5. Both CFRP face sheets for the sandwich panel were manufactured from four layers, each with a thickness of 0.25 mm, of a 2x2 twill weave fabric with 0/90 orientation and cured separately and bonded to the full-size core in a second step, since the originally used thermoplastic (HT-PLA) for early stages proved to be inadequate under the thermal and pressure conditions of the autoclave process, as described above. The four core segments during the bonding process, as well as the completed vacuum sandwich panel with a final format of approximately 292 mm × 378 mm, are shown in Fig. 5. The thickness from the top to bottom facesheet of the panel is 22 mm.

Figure 5: (a) Bonding process of four core segments; (b) final vacuum sandwich panel

4 TESTING METHODOLOGY AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

4.1 Test Methodology

The objective of this experiment was to qualitatively assess the thermal insulation performance of a vacuum sandwich panel incorporating a 3D-printed evacuable honeycomb core under cryogenic boundary conditions, and to investigate the impact of vacuum loss on thermal behavior. To achieve this, the test was structured into four consecutive load cases, each representing a distinct system state. The load cases are summarized in Table 1, along with relevant remarks regarding the temperature measurement approach:

Load Case	LC Description	Remarks on temperature measurement
LC 0	Calibration of thermocouples	with ice water / not displayed
LC 1	Evacuation of sandwich core at RT	with vacuum insulation
LC 2	Filling LN ₂ / Thermal Equilibrium	with vacuum insulation
LC 3	Active venting of sandwich core / simulation of vacuum failure	without vacuum insulation

Table 1: Thermal Vacuum Insulation Test – Load Cases

4.2 Experimental Setup

Test Sample Configuration

To perform the vacuum insulation test, a dedicated test setup was constructed. For this purpose, a container was built made of four structural foam plates and afterwards bonded to the top CFRP facesheet of the composite sandwich panel with a paste adhesive to form a basin to hold LN₂ to expose the top CFRP facesheet to cryogenic temperatures. Vacuum and pressure ports were integrated in the bottom CFRP facesheet, which can be seen in **Fig. 6**.

Figure 6: LN₂ foam basin and sandwich plate with ports

The principle test scheme, the temperature couples and placement of ports is given in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Thermal Vacuum Insulation Test – Test Setup

Temperature Measurement System

Temperature measurement was carried out using in total four thermocouples:

- TC1: ambient reference temperature, in 2m distance to test sample
- TC2 and TC4: located at the left and right edges of the bottom CFRP facesheet,
- TC3: located at the geometric center of the bottom CFRP facesheet.

with the following configuration:

- Sensor type: Thermocouple DT/G-TypK-2.0, Ø 2.0 mm
 - Nominal temperature range: -200 °C to +1100 °C
 - Calibration: Performed in an ice–water bath prior to testing (LC0)
 - Measurement limitation: Signal range limited to -55 °C due to DAQ configuration
- Data Acquisition System
 - Manufacturer: Gantner Instruments
 - Module type: Q.Brixx
 - Sampling & logging: via Gantner Q.station controller/Mlab software; post-processing MATLAB

Vacuum System

Evacuation of the sandwich core was performed using the following configuration:

- Pump type: Pfeiffer Duo 20M rotary vane pump
 - Nominal pumping speed: 21 m³/h
 - Ultimate pressure (w/ gas ballast): $\sim 1 \times 10^{-2}$ mbar

In the present test setup, the pump was connected to a CF40 port located at the bottom CFRP facesheet of the sandwich panel while the pressure sensor was connected to a CF16 port.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before the start of the experiment, all thermocouples were calibrated using ice water, and accurate temperature readings were confirmed by comparison with the ambient hall thermometer. During the measurement, a fourth thermocouple (TC1) served as a reference for monitoring the ambient hall temperature. The temperature–time evolution recorded during the vacuum insulation experiment is shown in Figure 3. Temperature areas above 0°C are shown in light red, while temperature areas below 0°C are shown in light blue. The duration of the different load cases is separated by black vertical lines.

Figure 8: Thermal Vacuum Insulation Test – Temperature Measurement Results

Within the first 20 minutes of the test, during LC1, the sandwich panel was evacuated at room temperature condition and a steady pressure level of 1.7 mbar was reached in the panel. No significant

change in panel temperature was observed during this phase, confirming that no relevant thermal flux occurred prior to LN₂ filling and that all sensors operated correctly. Afterwards the vacuum pump was shut off.

During load case LC2, liquid nitrogen (LN₂) was filled in the LN₂ basin, leading to a rapid decrease in temperature at the bottom CFRP facesheet, as heat was conducted through the panel toward the fluid-sided top CFRP facesheet (−196 °C). After approximately 20 minutes, a quasi-steady thermal gradient was reached, characterized by the horizontal lines of temperature measurements of TC2-TC4. and approximately 0 °C, as recorded by TC3 at the bottom facesheet. For the single thermocouples the following temperatures were measured

- TC3 (center): 0.5 °C
- TC2 (left edge): 2.4 °C
- TC4 (right edge): 9.3 °C

This clear temperature difference between the fluid-sided top CFRP facesheet and the ambient-facing bottom CFRP facesheet indicates the panel’s effective thermal insulation under vacuum condition. Slight asymmetries between TC2 and TC4 are attributed to edge effects. The pressure in the core dropped further to 0.86 mbar.

In load case LC3, active ventilation of the honeycomb core was initiated to ambient pressure condition. As a result, all three thermocouples (TC2–TV4) on the bottom face sheet exhibited an immediate and pronounced further decrease in temperature. Due to the signal range limitation in the DAQ setting (−55 °C), the lower threshold of measurement was quickly exceeded, leading to a loss of valid data below that limit.

- TC3 (center): −55.0 °C, within 9 minutes after loss of vacuum
- TC2 (left edge): −55.0 °C within 17 minutes after loss of vacuum
- TC4 (right edge): −48.2 °C by the end of LC3

In addition to the thermal measurements, visual observations revealed significant frost formation on the lower surface of the specimen, as shown in **Fig. 9** during LC3. This frost accumulation is attributed to the condensation and subsequent freezing of atmospheric moisture, driven by the steep thermal gradient across the face sheet during actively induced vacuum loss

Figure 9: Thermal Vacuum Insulation Test – LC3: Frosting of bottom face sheet

The experiment confirms the proof-of-concept for a 3D-printed, evacuated honeycomb core as an integrated thermal insulation layer for cryogenic applications. Under vacuum conditions, the sandwich structure maintained a thermal gradient of nearly 200 K across a panel thickness of just 22 mm, with only minimal heat flux through the core. These results highlight the effectiveness of vacuum sandwich panels with 3D-printed evacuable cores in suppressing thermal conduction and enabling stable cryogenic temperature separation, although the sample configuration with HT-PLA as early test was not ideal. The steady-state pressure inside the core during Load Case 1 reached 1.7 mbar, which was higher than the nominal ultimate pressure of the vacuum pump. This deviation is attributed to internal outgassing from the polymer structure, in particular moisture and volatile components in the HT-PLA material, as well as anticipated minor line losses due to reduction in cross-section of the vacuum piping. The sandwich core was not pre-conditioned (e.g. by thermal bakeout), which further explains the elevated residual pressure despite continuous evacuation. In contrast, the rapid temperature decrease observed in Load Case 3, following intentional, active venting of the sandwich core, revealed the concept's sensitivity to vacuum integrity. Once the vacuum was lost, the insulation effect deteriorated within minutes, leading to a nearly uniform cryogenic transition on the ambient-facing side of the panel. This clearly illustrates the binary behavior of vacuum-based insulation systems and their dependence on stable pressure containment. Overall, the findings demonstrate that 3D-printed vacuum sandwich systems offer substantial insulation potential for use in cryogenic composite pressure vessels, as long as long-term vacuum sealing, structural robustness, and environmental durability can be ensured. While the insulation performance under vacuum was excellent, the observed failure mode highlights a key design constraint for aerospace implementation

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The proposed vacuum-insulated CFRP sandwich panel with 3D-printed, evacuable honeycomb core was successfully tested. Results show that such structures can offer both high insulation performance and structural function, making them interesting for aerospace hydrogen tanks. Compared to foam or MLI, this concept offers superior integration potential, especially where tanks must carry load and interface with airframe structures, such as in fuselage integrated LH₂ tanks. The feasibility study successfully demonstrated the potential of a 3D-printed evacuable honeycomb vacuum core in a CFRP sandwich structure as cryogenic thermal insulation. The panel exhibited promising thermal resistance under vacuum and cryogenic temperatures. Compared to foam or MLI, the proposed system offers the unique ability to integrate insulation and mechanical function. This multifunctionality has high potential for aerospace LH₂ tanks subjected to both internal pressure and structural mounting in the airframe. Notable advantages include the design freedom for single and double-curved structures, the ability for local cell size refinement in areas with high structural demands, and the low outgassing behavior when using PEEK honeycombs. Main drawbacks are linked to loss of vacuum for such structures as intentionally induced in the LC3 load case, which is, however, a known challenge also for double-walled tanks with MLI. Additionally, the wall thickness is currently higher than that of conventional NOMEX honeycombs, negatively impacting mass efficiency. Furthermore, the component size is limited by the 3D printing hardware, necessitating segmentation for medium and large-scale structures. The material cost, especially when using PEEK, is also considerable. Nevertheless, the results provide a solid foundation for further investigations.

Therefore, the next steps will involve several focused investigations and development activities on flat samples for the 3D printed core and composite sandwich structure such as additional mechanical tests to evaluate flatwise tensile, compression and shear properties at room and cryogenic temperatures and under thermal cycling conditions. The work will also include investigations on wall thickness reduction methods and hence weight reduction and the manufacturing of single and double curved samples as well as small-scale CFRP technology demonstrator tanks. These will be used to simulate operational conditions and to verify both structural integrity and thermal behavior under realistic scenarios. In parallel, full thermal analyses will be performed.

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